

THE CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract: In the research paper the major concept of idiomatical aspect was to compare the degree of it in single idiomatic words and in phraseological units, while in discussing transformation possibilities the purpose was to show how phraseological units can be changed in semantic and lexical terms.

Key words: *the motivation of meaning, phraseological adhesions, phraseological unit, phraseological combinations, structural-semantic characteristics.*

INTRODUCTION.

Phraseological units or “idioms” as a school of scientists prioritize and the figurative meanings that they carry on have drawn the attention of many linguists. Phraseological units make up an important part of the English lexicon for they exist in both: literary and everyday languages. They also play a great role in language for they make it more vivid and more “colourful”.

In the modern linguistic world, there are some approaches to the classification of the phraseological units. For instance, V.V. Vinogradov was one of the linguist who presented the classification of phraseological turns of the Russian language in

terms of the motivation of the meaning of phraseological units. The motivation of the meanings of phraseological unity is based on different types of transfer (metaphor, metonymy, comparison), therefore this type of word combinations is distinguished by semantic duality. [1;24]

METHODS.

V.V.Vinogradov identifies the following types of phraseological units: 1. Phraseological adhesions; 2. Phraseological unity; 3. Phraseological combinations.

While, the classification system of phraseological units proffered by Professor A.V. Koonin is based on the combined structural-semantic principle and it also considers the quotient of stability of phraseological units. Professor A.V. Koonin defines a phraseological units as a stable word group with wholly or partially transferred the meaning. [2;343]

In his classification phraseological units are subdivided into classes, subclasses and types. Classes are distinguished according to their function in communication determined by their structural-semantic characteristics.

Nominative phraseological units - are represented by word-groups, including the ones with one meaningful word, e.g. “*a bull in a china shop*” “a person who is careless, or who moves or acts in a rough or awkward way”. All units of this kind class denote objects, states, qualities and the like. The first class also includes word-groups with a predicative structure, such as “*as the crow flies*” “in a

straight line’, and, also, partially predicative phrases of the type “*see how the land lies*” - to try to discover what the situation really is before you make a decision, “*ships that pass in the night*” - chance acquaintances.

Phraseological units of this class fall into the following subclasses:

- substantive: “*crocodile tears*” – if someone sheds crocodile tears, they seem sad, sorry, or upset, but they do not really feel this way;
- adjectival: “*as good as gold*” – (informal) behaving in a way that other people approve of;

– adverbial: “*by & by* “-(old-fashioned) before long; soon, “*to and fro*” - backwards and forwards;

– verbal: “*to go Deutch* “-(informal) to share the cost of something, especially a meal, equally.

Thus, classification by A. V. Koonin is of a comprehensive character.

There are phraseological units, expressing statement, that have the form of a complete sentence. A. V. Koonin calls them communicative. Among communicative phraseological units two groups of expressions are distinguished: proverbs and sayings.

Another linguist Professor Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units according to the functional principle. [3. 368] Two groups are distinguished:

1) phraseological units

2) idioms.

Phraseological units are neutral, non-metaphorical when compared to idioms: *get up*(rise from bed after sleeping), *fall asleep*(to sleep without intending to). Idioms are metaphoric, stylistically coloured: *to take the bull by the horns* (to deal with a difficult situation in a very direct way) , *to beat about the bush*(to discuss a matter without coming to the point), *to bark up the wrong tree*(to mistake one`s object).

Structurally prof. Smirnitsky distinguishes one-summit (one-member) and many-summit (two member, three-member, etc.) phraseological units, depending on the number of notional words: *against the grain*, *to carry the day*, *to have all one`s eggs in one basket*.

Let us pay attention to the fact that, having completely different origins, phraseological units are endowed with a number of properties that cannot be overlooked. T.Z. Cherdantseva draws attention to the following important properties inherent in phraseological units:

1) *Variation*: Variants are understood as varieties of the same unit, which, while fully preserving the identity of meaning and image, may have differences in component composition. The following types of variants of phraseological units can

be distinguished: phonetic, morphological, lexical, lexico-syntactic, lexico-semantic. As an example, phrase- semantic field of expression of joy, happiness and delight in Uzbek phraseological world picture can be seen in several variants: “*og`zi qulog`iga yetdi*” (literally, the mouth has reached the ears),” *boshi ko`kka yetdi*”(literally, the head reached the sky) or “*terisiga sig`madi*”(literally, do not fit on the skin).

2) *Ambiguity*: It occurs when the image is able to evoke different associations depending on the situation reflected in the statement. For example, the phraseology “*play with fire*” can mean both “to set a fire” and “to have a risk with doing something to someone”;

3) *Synonymy*: With synonymy, phraseological units need only a common meaning (a neutral equivalent, an ideogram), while the component composition does not coincide. The general neutral component assumes that phraseological units are capable of denoting the same characteristic or sensation, but in each case they are transmitted in a new perspective. For example, a phraseological unit, the general neutral component of which is “*to be in love*” or “*to fall in love*” sevib qolmoq ,

4) *Homonymy*: Cases of homonymy within the phraseological system are quite rare. As an example, “*yoqasini ushlamoq*” can be understood either “grab the collar” or “to be surprised”. In order to know the meaning of the phraseologic unit correctly, we should pay attention to the context.

DISCUSSION.

From scientific observations I can sum up that , according to the semantic feature of phraseological units, from the classification of V.V. Vinogradov, can be divided into phraseological merges, phraseological unities and phraseological combinations. We share the point of view of A.V.Koonin that his classification phraseological units are subdivided into classes, subclasses and types which are distinguished according to their function in communication determined by their structural-semantic characteristics. It should be noted that Professor Smirnitsky classifies phraseological units into 2 parts according to the functional principle, while

T.Z. Cherdantseva observes the important properties inherent in phraseological units such as variation, ambiguity, synonymy and homonymy.

CONCLUSION.

Linguists define the concept of “phraseological unit” as a universal name for combinations of words related semantically, which differ from other syntactic constructions in that they are reproduced in speech in a fixed ratio of lexicogrammatical composition and semantic structure.

REFERENCES

1. Арсентьева Е.Ф. Фразеология и фразеография в сопоставительном аспекте (на материале русского и английского языков). – Казань, 2006. – 253 с.
2. Арсентьева Е.Ф. Сопоставительный анализ фразеологических единиц. – Казань, 1989. – 125 с.
3. Ganiyeva Sh.A. The structure of Uzbek phraseologisms (modelling by form and meaning): The dissertation thesis (PhD). – Fergana, 2017. – p. 50.
4. Кунин А. В. Английская фразеология. (Теорет. курс.) М., «Высшая школа», 1970. – 343с.
5. Khudoyberdievna, S. Z. (2021). Phraseologization as Cognitive Process. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 1, 22-26.
6. Кунин А.В. О фразеологической номинации // Фразеологическая семантика: Сб. науч. тр. – М., 1983. Вып. 211. – С. 99–100.
7. Radjabova M.A. Semantic analysis of phraseological units with onomastic components.
8. Radjabova M.A. Comparative Study Of Phraseological Units With Naming Features In Nonrelated Languages // *Philology Matters*. – 2019. – Т. 2019. – №. 1. – С. 71-80.
9. Rustamova M.M. Phraseology as an Object of Linguistic and Cultural Studies *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology (IJRASET) Volume 10 Issue XI Nov 2022*

10. Saidova Z. Classification of verbal phraseological units denoting the emotional state of a person -International Scientific Conference,December 18-19– 2021.
11. Vinogradov V.V. Izbrannietrudi. Leksikologiyaileksikografiya. – M. : Nauka, 1977 – 198 s.
12. Khasanovna, K. E. TYPOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF LANGUAGE. *INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM*, 46.
13. Umbarov, I., Karimov, F., Karimov, Z., Bekkamov, M., Ubaydullayev, A., Eshkuvatov, E., & Israilova, D. (2024). Gravity grain cleaning machine and its importance in grain logistics and sustainable agriculture. In *BIO Web of Conferences* (Vol. 105, p. 06016). EDP Sciences.
14. Rustamova, N., Inoyatova, S., Madazizova, D., Israilova, D., & Israilov, S. (2024). Genetically modified ecosystems: Innovative approaches in agriculture and their environmental impact. In *BIO Web of Conferences* (Vol. 149, p. 01063). EDP Sciences.
15. Khursheed, S., Sharma, S., Paul, V. K., Alzubaidi, L. H., & Israilova, D. (2024). Review of the factors inducing delay in construction project material management. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 563, p. 02044). EDP Sciences.
16. Balaji, V., Padala, S., Josh, S. K., Muhsen, M., Singh, S., Isroilova, B., & Israilova, D. (2024). Finite element analysis of double pipe heat exchanger using nanofluids. In *E3S Web of Conferences* (Vol. 563, p. 01004). EDP Sciences.